

Direct-Detection Receiver for 16-QAM Modulated Signals

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Abstract We demonstrate a novel receiver for detecting 16-QAM modulated signals. The received signal is split into branches for phase and intensity detection. The signal in the phase branch is converted into a PAM7 signal, and a standard PAM4 signal is detected in the intensity branch. ©2024 The Author(s)

Introduction

The exponential growth of intra-datacenter traffic demands simple and efficient interconnect solutions which are capable of supporting the need of high-performance computing and artificial intelligence applications^[1]. To address those demands, there has been several investigations targeting efficient modulation using novel electro-optic materials^{[2],[3]}, and high-speed operation of existing modulators enabled by analog or digital electronic equalizers^{[4],[5]}. These investigations target the use of standard intensity-modulation direct detection systems such as 4-level pulse amplitude modulation (PAM4) which are widely used inside datacenters. Additionally, there have been several efforts to develop simplified coherent systems for intra-datacenter interconnects, known as coherent-lite systems^{[6],[7]}. Although coherent-lite systems allow high-capacity transmission using a single laser, they remain technologically complex as they still require the use of a high-power local oscillator laser at the receiver, and complex digital-signal processor (DSP). Previously, we have demonstrated direct-detection of quadrature phase shift keying (QPSK) modulated signals using a passive spectral filter^[8].

In this paper, we propose and experimentally demonstrate a direct-detection receiver for 16-level quadrature amplitude modulated (16QAM) signals. We discuss the receiver architecture and characterization, and analyse the system through bit-error ratio measurements and simulations.

Device structure

A schematic diagram of the proposed direct-detection receiver is shown in Fig. 1(a). A grating coupler is used to couple the received 16QAM signal onto the photonic integrated circuit (PIC). The signal is then split into intensity and phase detection branches using a 50:50 splitter. The phase detection branch consists of a semiconductor optical amplifier (SOA), a ring resonator, and a photodiode followed by a transimpedance amplifier (TIA).

The intensity detection branch consists of a photodiode followed by TIA. The electrical signals from the TIAs are converted into the digital domain for further signal processing. An optical microscope image of the our PIC is shown in Fig. 1(b). The PIC is based on silicon photonics technology fabricated at Advanced Micro Foundry (AMF). The light path on the chip is highlighted by using white lines. An image of our PIC packaged together with a commercial TIA die on a high-speed printed circuit board is shown in Fig. 1(c). A 16-channel fiber-array is coupled to the chip using a grating-assisted quasi-planar coupler.

Fig. 1: (a) Schematic diagram of the proposed direct-detection receiver circuit consisting of the phase and intensity detection branches. (b) Optical microscope image of the silicon photonic chip. (c) Image of our silicon photonic chip packaged together with a TIA die on a high-speed printed circuit board including fiber-to-chip coupling.

Working principle

The key part of our receiver circuit is the ring resonator that allows to convert a phase-modulated signal into an intensity-modulated signal by spectral filtering. The signal spectrum and the resonance frequency of the ring resonator are spectrally aligned to implement efficient sideband filtering, which converts the phase-modulated signal to an intensity-modulated signal. We have previously reported the conversion of quadrature phase shift keying (QPSK) modulated signals into 7-level pulse amplitude modulated signals (PAM7)^[8]. For

Fig. 2: Schematic diagram of the experimental setup. Light from a tunable laser source (TLS) is modulated using a cascaded phase and intensity modulators to generate a star-16QAM signal. The resulting signal is sent to the direct detection receiver. The received electrical signal is sampled using a real-time sampling oscilloscope.

our receiver to detect 16QAM, the symbols need to be arranged in a star-16QAM format which allows our receiver to treat phase and intensity modulated signals separately. The star-16QAM constellation diagram is shown in the inset of Fig. 1. This constellation consists of four amplitude levels, and four phase values which gives a total combination of 16 symbols. In the intensity detection branch, the photodiode detects a PAM4 signal. As the phase modulation is implemented using a pure-phase modulator, phase modulated symbols will not be detected by the photodiode in the intensity detection branch. In the phase detection branch, a saturated SOA is used to suppress amplitude modulation of the received signal. This amplitude-equalized signal is then sent to the ring resonator for phase-to-intensity modulation conversion via spectral filtering. The resulting intensity-modulated signal, i.e., PAM7 signal, is then detected by a photodiode. In the digital domain, a lookup table^[8] is used to map the 7-levels of the signal into the four symbols of the phase modulation.

Star-16QAM generation and detection setup

The experimental setup for 16QAM signal generation and detection is shown in Fig. 2. Light from a tunable laser source centered around the telecom C-band is modulated using a cascade of bulk lithium niobate based phase and intensity modulators. Two different sets of 10 Gbd electrical PAM4 signals generated by a 65 GSa/s arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) are used as modulating input signals to the phase and intensity modulators to generate a star-16QAM signal. A pseudo random bit sequence (PRBS) length of $2^{15} - 1$ is used for each PAM4 signal. The eye-diagram of the electrical PAM4 signal generated using the AWG is shown in the inset of Fig. 2. The generated star-16QAM signal is then amplified using an erbium-doped fiber amplifier (EDFA) to compensate for insertion losses of the modulators. Out-of-band amplified spontaneous emission

noise is eliminated by using a 3 nm band-pass filter. The signal is then launched through a fiber link ranging from 500 meters to 10 km. The power of the received signal is controlled by a variable optical attenuator (VOA). As the PIC is polarization sensitive due to the grating couplers used, manual polarization control is required to ensure maximum optical power coupling to the chip.

The device under test (DUT) is slightly different from the schematics shown in Fig. 1(a). The main difference is that the SOA and the 50:50 splitter are off-chip fiber optic discrete components. Therefore, the phase and the intensity branches are directly accessible via two grating couplers as shown using the optical microscope image of Fig. 1(b). After detection of the signals using on-chip photodiodes, the resulting photocurrent is converted into voltage and amplified by a TIA die before being sampled by a 80 GSa/s digital storage oscilloscope (DSO). A digital communication analyzer (DCA) is used to monitor the signal quality via eyediagrams.

Results

The results of our experiments are presented in Fig. 3 using eyediagrams and bit-error ratio (BER) for back-to-back (B2B) measurements. For a transmitted star-16QAM signal, the received eyediagrams for the PAM7 and PAM4 signals corresponding to the phase and intensity detection branches are shown in Fig. 3(a) and (b), respectively. BER versus received optical power curves are shown for four measurements in Fig. 3(c). The intensity detection branch is tested for the case in which we have enabled or disabled phase modulation. Here, the phase modulation corresponds to the QPSK-modulation format. This phase (QPSK) modulation is combined with intensity (PAM4) modulation to provide a star-16QAM signal. The BER measurements for the PAM4 signals show that the presence of phase modulations has negligible impact on the intensity detection branch. A BER of 1×10^{-5} , which is below the KR4 forward-error

correction (FEC) limit, is achieved at -11 dBm received optical power.

Fig. 3: (a) Eyediagram of the measured PAM7 signal from the phase detection branch. (b) Eyediagram of the measured PAM4 signal from the intensity detection branch. (c) BER vs received optical power for B2B measurement of intensity and phase detection branches of the 16-QAM signal.

Measured BER versus received optical power curves for the PAM7 signal of the phase detection branch is shown in Fig. 3(c). Similar to the PAM4 measurements, we have characterized the performance of the phase detection branch with and without the presence of intensity modulation. For the case in which we detect QPSK, we have bypassed the SOA as there is no need for amplitude equalization. A BER of 6.25×10^{-4} is achieved at -2.2 dBm received optical power for QPSK detection, c.f green curve Fig. 3(c). For the phase detection of the star-16QAM signal, we measured a BER of 5.4×10^{-3} at -4 dBm received optical power. There is a 1 dB penalty for detecting 16-QAM compared to QPSK detection at 7% overhead hard-decision threshold. A 7-Tap and 21-Tap $T/2$ -spaced feed-forward linear equalizer based on least-mean-square algorithm is used to compensate signal impairments from the transmitter and receiver for the PAM4 and the PAM7 signals, respectively. The phase detection branch has about 12 dB power penalty compared to the intensity detection branch as shown in Fig. 3(c). This is due to in-efficient modulators used in our transmitter that require large half-wave voltages and have limited electro-optic bandwidth. Additionally, our receiver demonstrator has excessively long wire-bonds between our PIC and the TIA die which deteriorate the signal-integrity of the received signal.

Fig. 4 shows Monte Carlo simulation of BER versus signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) per bit comparing QPSK detection using the phase detection branch,

and standard PAM4 detection. A random symbol sequence of 1×10^6 symbols are generated, and a rectangular pulse shaping filter is implemented at 50 Gbd. The signal is then low-pass filtered by a 4th-order Bessel filter for generating smooth PAM4 drive signal. The resulting electrical signal then drives a Mach-Zehnder modulator. The main sources of noise in the system are shot noise and thermal noise of photodiodes, and quantization errors of the analog-to-digital converters. We have benchmarked our simulation model with previously reported theoretical results^[9]. The receiver DSP implementation includes low-pass filtering with a cutoff frequency at the baudrate, clock recovery, a 3-Tap $T/2$ -spaced feed-forward linear equalizer, symbol (de)mapping, and error counting. Our QPSK detection have similar BER performance as PAM4 systems at high SNR values, while at low SNR values there is a power penalty. This is due to our detection method that depends on the correct detection of the previous symbol. If the previously detected symbol is erroneous, subsequent symbols will also be erroneous until a unique transition is reached.

Fig. 4: Monte Carlo simulation of bit-error ratio vs signal-to-noise ratio per bit comparing a standard PAM4, and phase detection branch with QPSK to PAM7 conversion at 50 Gbd.

Conclusion

We have demonstrated a direct-detection receiver for star-16QAM modulated signals. The receiver splits the received signal into intensity and phase detection branches, and exploit a novel phase-to-intensity converter realized using ring resonator on silicon photonics platform. Furthermore, a saturated SOA is used to limit amplitude modulation in the phase detection branch. Our experimental demonstration is currently limited to 10 Gbd operation due to the requirement of large half-wave voltage, and limited bandwidth of our optical modulators. The receiver significantly simplifies the detection of coherently modulated optical signals and avoids the need for a local oscillator laser, and complex DSP for short-reach communication.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge financial support from Innovation Foundation Denmark, and the European Research Council via grant agreement numbers 834410-FANO, and 101067399 - Fano Detector. Furthermore, the authors would like to thank Chip Integration Technology Center (CITC), NL for packaging our demonstrator, and Kjeld Dalgaard for reviewing our printed circuit board design, and developing electronic control board.

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